

	<p>Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration</p>
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Final TRIPLE conference

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Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
KER	Key Exploitable Results
MWS	Max Weber Stiftung
PID	Persistent Identifier
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WP	Work Package

Publishable Summary

Deliverable 1.5 focuses on the results of the final TRIPLE conference held in Bonn from February 1st to 3rd 2023. During the project, the MWS, in charge of the communication of the TRIPLE project, organised two public conferences, to convey the achievements of the tasks.

The first public conference was held online due to covid restrictions, from November 22 to 24, 2021¹. The title of the conference was : “Empowering discovery in open social sciences and humanities”. The aim of this conference was to discuss the impact, benefits and challenges of discovery services for the social sciences and humanities (SSH), in the European research ecosystem. Members of the Open Science and SSH communities (researchers, university and library staff) as well as other TRIPLE stakeholders such as publishers, science journalists, SMEs, public authorities and policy makers have met and discussed the topic of innovative multilingualism and multicultural discovery solution for the SSH –, crowdfunding in science, business models for Open Science, the role of SSH in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and of course to showcase the nascent GoTriple platform.

The second and final TRIPLE conference was devoted to improving discovery and collaboration in Open Science. It took place in Bonn in early February 2023 to celebrate the first chapter of the GoTriple platform. In conjunction with the closing session of the TRIPLE project (1st October 2019-31 March 2023), the conference also gave the opportunity to think of ways to improve collaboration beyond the field of SSH research.

The organisation of the final conference reflects all the work accomplished during the project and specific material has been made available publicly :

- TRIPLE brochure
- Conference website
- Publications of the papers on Zenodo

The purpose of this deliverable is not to give an overview of the contents of the different sessions but rather how it has been organised and present the main aspects and outcomes of the event. It is composed of three main sections :

- Aim and outline of the conference
- Scientific content and the perspectives that this event has opened up
- Potential opportunities for collaboration

¹ <https://project.gotriple.eu/triple-international-conference-2021>

1 | AIM AND OUTLINE OF THE CONFERENCE

The preparation of the conference, led by the TRIPLE partner MWS, started in March 2022. From the beginning, all work put into the preparation aimed to shape the event as an occasion to share the results of the TRIPLE project, especially the Key Exploitable Results (KER), with the broader Open Science community and engage with stakeholders beyond the reach of the project. Following this aim, the organisational team aimed to create an impact beyond the end of the TRIPLE project in March 2023.

The conference was planned as a hybrid event for the 1-3 of February 2023 and a task force led by WP8 leader was assembled to work on its preparation. First task was to prepare the Call for Papers, which was to be launched in September 2022. After drafting the call and running it through various feedback loops to secure the quality and publish a call which addresses the right target groups, the final call was disseminated in the end of September 2022, focussing on two crucial aspects of Open Science: discovery and collaboration. The conference was thereby titled “Improving Discovery and Collaboration in Open Science”. The call itself was explicitly drafted to appeal to a diverse range of members of the academic community, such as researchers, members of partner institutions and other infrastructure providers, asking for contributions to topics such as sustainability, collaboration, data quality and innovation. The goal of this multifaceted call for papers was to attract a wider audience, e.g. introducing members of non-SSH disciplines to the results of the TRIPLE project, in particular to GoTriple, thereby inducing collaboration that would stretch beyond the GoTriple users and SSH community. The call was disseminated via TRIPLE and OPERAS, the OPERAS national nodes, the TRIPLE project partners, social media and via mailing lists targeting national audiences, a communication measure coordinated by members of WP8.

Figure 1 : Picture of the final TRIPLE conference invitation

The taskforce handling the organisation of the conference was expanded in October 2022 to support the WP8 leader with daily tasks regarding the preparation.

More than 20 abstracts were submitted for the call, two were accepted as workshop sessions, two were accepted as poster submissions and 12 as presentations. The deadline for the call, originally on November 30, was slightly extended to December 4, 2022, to allow for more than 10 additional

submissions. All submissions were peer-reviewed by members of the TRIPLE Advisory Board (TAB) and TRIPLE consortium members depending on their expertise.

Being a hybrid event, participants who could not travel to the conference location were able to attend the conference via a Zoom stream provided to them. In total, 154 participants registered to the conference, 90 of them attended in person while 31 attended the event virtually. 19 European countries were represented and 34 institutions were not part of the TRIPLE consortium. These figures stand out from the usual proportion where only half of the registrants actually participate in the event. Also, the fact that a significant number of participants are not part of the consortium illustrates the interest of the project and the platform within the European SSH community.

The conference opened with a speech² by the scientific coordinator of the project, Suzanne Dumouchel, which replaced the need of a discovery platform like GoTriple in the general context, both scientific and societal, in which we are living. By highlighting the changes in societies between the beginning and the end of the project (COVID crisis, war in Ukraine, etc.), the talk presented the role of GoTriple in better understanding these changes.

The presentations are deposited on Zenodo and are accessible in open access. All speakers gave their formal agreement to reuse and share their presentations, while a takeaway brochure³ was printed and distributed. This brochure sums up the features of the platform, its objectives and impacts and gives direct access to the TRIPLE APIs, controlled vocabulary, training toolkit and main scientific publications. A brochure featuring all abstracts, the programme and biographies of the presenters has been uploaded on Zenodo as well as all presentations are available on Zenodo.⁴

1.1 IMPROVING DISCOVERY

The conference programme mirrored the ambition of covering a wide array of aspects that connect to the TRIPLE project:⁵ On the first day, a demo of the GoTriple platform was given by the project manager, Emilie Blotière, and GoTriple ambassador Agnieszka Szulińska at the beginning of the event followed by a first keynote lecture by Leslie Chan (University of Toronto) on the topic of 'Platform and Knowledge Production in the Age of AI'. The day concluded with a panel session on Scholarly Communication and a poster session. The second day of the conference featured another keynote lecture by Andrea Rapp (TU Darmstadt) on the topic of 'Research Communities, Visibility and Infrastructure: The Impact of Open Science' followed by four parallel sessions of panels and workshops on topics such as training and reusability, data and metadata, collaboration in SSH and beyond and more. The last day of the conference concluded with a final keynote lecture by Ari Asmi (Research Data Alliance) on the topic of 'Internationalising European Open Science initiatives: A decade of Research Data Alliance, followed by presentations and workshops on topics such as multilingualism, how to become a GoTriple Provider and more.

Several institutions presented their research tool or service and highlighted the interdisciplinary and interoperability of the latter.

² Dumouchel, Suzanne. (2023). TRIPLE Conference "Improving Discovery and Collaboration in Open Science" (1-3 February 2023). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704572>

³ TRIPLE conference Key Takeaways : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711891>

⁴ TRIPLE conference brochure: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711891>

⁵ <https://project.gotriple.eu/past-events/triple-international-conference-2023/the-conference-program/>

For instance, the SMW⁶ tool from the Giessen University library presented by Michael Freiberg is a good example of an interoperable and open source research tool to address the needs of scholarly communication in collaboration, multilingualism, scholarly publishing and research data management data. Its potentialities in the Social Sciences and Humanities open science were discussed notably with data scientists and computer engineers who developed GoTriple.

Interdisciplinary and collaborative research methodology was also highlighted in the presentation of Caroline Delmazo from COIMBRA University about ReSEED project⁷. It aims to investigate socio-economic changes and the path of cultivated seeds from the new worlds to Europe, mainly in the Iberian Peninsula, requires knowledge of many disciplines which led the consortium to create partnerships with a gastronomy school and an initiative using genomics analysis interesting for ReSEED.

1.2. ENHANCE COLLABORATION

OPERAS-GER, the OPERAS national node in Germany, organised a World Café under the title *"It's German coffee and cake o'clock – chatting openly about Discovery with Representatives from Germany"* (18 attendees). The *"German coffee and cake o'clock"* was an opportunity for participants to connect, exchange knowledge and learn from each other's experiences. It gathered six representatives from German national search engines and research data infrastructures/services (1) Bielefeld Academic Search Engine, (2) consortia text+ of the German National Data Infrastructure, (3) Fachinformationsdienst Benelux (specialised information service Benelux), (4) publication platform PUBLISSO, (5) GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, (6) communication and information services for historians h-sozkult and clio-online.

Several individuals from the TRIPLE community connected with the consortia of text+ to exchange contacts to collaborate (see: <https://www.text-plus.org/en/networking/research-network/>) and two repositories were integrated afterwards into the GoTriple platform (h-sozkult and clio-online).

The main challenges in the German research landscape have become clear: institutions are often organised and connected within the German research landscape very well, but international or European wide collaboration mostly is done via networks, and not as individual institutions. Many of these networks are aggregated in bigger platforms such as BASE, which are already integrated in GoTriple platform. By the end of the session, it was evident that such exchanges are important to create synergies and common initiatives and the final TRIPLE conference provided such an opportunity. Furthermore, the GoTriple platform can offer a unique service and global perspective to the German community (or national communities in general), especially regarding multilingualism.

This session also raised awareness of GoTriple for the German audience via intermediaries such as the representatives who were invited. All of these participants are involved in several different networks and have contact with different stakeholders. Part of the discussion was also dedicated to the main role of the national node to ensure the alignment with the needs and requirements of the German SSH community.

⁶ Semantic Media Wiki research tool

⁷ ReSEED-Rescuing seeds'heritage - <https://reseed.uc.pt/>

1.3 POST-EVENT EVALUATION

A post-event evaluation was prepared and sent to all registered participants soon after the end of the conference. The evaluation form was created in Google Forms and aimed at documenting satisfaction from the event overall and the quality of the presentations, their relevance to participants’ work and opportunities for collaboration that emerged from the conference. The evaluation was left open for two weeks to allow participants time to fill it in and revisit their experience. Overall, 49 participants filled in the evaluation.

The evaluation form included four questions on the background of the participants (role in conference and demographics) and communications (how did they hear about the conference), followed by eight questions on the content of the conference and its quality. The answers of the survey came from participants with an active role in the conference, session chairs etc (44,9%), onsite participants (30,6%) and online participants (24,5%). Most of the project partner countries were represented at the conference and in the answers collected in this evaluation form, with the majority coming from Germany (11 answers), Italy (8 answers) and France (7 answers). Not surprisingly, the majority of the answers came from academia (33 answers) though other sectors were also represented such as Governmental organisations, NGOs and Private SMEs etc.

Post-event evaluation indicated that the event was generally received very positively. When asked if the expectation of the participant was fulfilled, 96% chose “I strongly agree” or “I agree” with only 4% opting for the answer “neutral”.

Figure 2: Diagramme from the evaluation form no. 1

Again 96% of the 49 participants filling out the evaluation either strongly agreed or agreed with the statement “The content of the TRIPLE2023 conference was relevant to my daily work” as shown in the figure below.

Figure 3: Diagramme from the evaluation form no.2

When asked about how satisfied they were with the overall event programme, most of those who participated in the survey described their satisfaction level as high on a scale from 1 to 5 (1=low, 5=high).

Figure 4 : bar chart from the evaluation form no.4

The survey concluded with three open questions on ‘what did you like most about the event and why’, ‘what did you like less of the event and why’ and comments and suggestions to share with the event organisers. The comments received again were very positive with people stressing the quality and inspiring talks of the keynote speakers and the project coordinator, the excellent organisation of the event, the openness and friendly atmosphere. In terms of the second and last questions, some comments received had to do with the hybrid aspect of the event, e.g. providing online participants with more opportunities to feel included and network with the other participants. Other than that, participants were very positively impressed by the level of organisation and the quality of the conference.

The social media coverage of the final TRIPLE conference generated considerable outreach for the project. The 30 Twitter posts posted from the 1-3 February 2023 gained 18.000 impressions, and were shared 107 times. The TRIPLE account gained 11 followers during the span of the conference, which translates to a follower growth of 1,27% in only three days.⁸

⁸ These numbers have been acquired via Hootsuite Analytics.

Figure 5 : Post Impressions for TRIPLE Twitter Account from 1-3 February 2023

The project website and GoTriple.eu recorded a considerable gain in traffic over the three days of the final conference:⁹ In comparison to the previous months of RP3 , GoTriple counted 311 visits, 67,2% more than in the previous three days before the conference. 1,319 page views were counted from 1-3 February 2023 with 443 total searches being run via the platform. Again, in comparison to the parallel time span of three days preceding the conference this is an increase by 139,5%.

For the TRIPLE project website the numbers increased as well: In comparison to the three days ahead of the conference 353 visits to the website were counted, translating to an increase of 239,4%. 629 page views were recorded, increasing the numbers of the three days period compared by 222,6%.

⁹ All of the following stats have been acquired by Matomo Analytics.

2 | SCIENTIFIC CONTENT

2.1 DATA

In total the conference hosted four workshops (between 8 and 20 attendees for each workshop). Three of these were devoted to data to improve both the quality of the data generated by the platform (keywords, controlled vocabularies), and also the ones indexed and coming from a large range of data providers. Two workshops were especially devoted to the current and future GoTriple data providers to improve the quality of the data by discussing with users and data providers and coming into concrete recommendations such as the presentation of a specific web application (Harvesting Management System) to ease the onboarding of new providers. Real prospect users attended to live test the integration of their repositories in GoTriple.

A large space was left to data in general and in the improvement of data quality in particular, TRIPLE participants and non TRIPLE participants met to present their work and difficulties to build a tool or service that meets at the same time accessibility, interoperability, reusability and quality. IBL-PAN, Net7 notably and the TRIPLE data officer, Arnaud Gingold, chaired panel sessions and workshops to share experiences. IBL PAN presented the role of open metadata in the SSH scholarly communication and current challenges in the context of the TRIPLE project such as the integration and harvesting of aggregators and repositories in GoTriple. They also discussed quality, scope and scientific reuse during a workshop dedicated to the GoTriple data quality (10 attendees). It was built upon the results of “The Workshop: Data quality work plan” which took place during the TRIPLE consortium meeting in Athens in September 2022. We agreed on additional data services that should be implemented and the GoTriple role in the SSH evaluation. In the second part, concrete recommendations were made related to the tangible solutions and action points such as new data providers and innovative data analysis solutions and GoTriple’s role for such stakeholders as academic libraries, data metrics providers or scientists engaged in data-based research.

The success of the platform depends on its adoption of course by users whether they are researchers, students, policy makers, journalists, entrepreneurs, business and industry leaders, and citizens. For this purpose GoTriple offers a large set of relevant classified and normalised SSH data and metadata, to allow new ways of research. The collaboration with data providers is of paramount importance for at least two reasons : convince them of being harvested by GoTriple and support them in the improvement of their data and metadata. For this reason, data providers were then at the core of the conference, while several workshops and presentations focused on how to improve the quality of the data and the harvesting management system.

Taina Jääskeläinen (CESSDA) also led a workshop about the CESSDA Data Catalogue: *What can be done at the catalogue end and what needs harmonised metadata?* 15 persons attended the discussion highlighting the usefulness of online general guidelines on creating SSH metadata and catalogues. Recommendations were shared at three levels :

- Metadata : provide standardised, machine-actionable information on language (e.g. ISO-standard tags) and geographical location (e.g. IANA tags) in metadata files. Provide also persistent identifiers for both the resource and the creators. Differentiate between organisation and individual creators.

- User interfaces : If the catalogue UI uses filters, inform users if the filtering is incomplete due to missing metadata (i.e. does not cover all resources). Accept
 and <p> html tags in textual elements in metadata to keep longer texts readable for users. Provide guidelines on how to handle multilinguality: UI, metadata ja data file languages.
- Provide information on available tools: For instance, validated language detection tools. Tools for matching multilingual textual geographical location information with standardised codes (e.g. GeoNames).

All data working sessions reported that FAIR principles and the increase of societal and economic impacts are at the core of the research projects such as the *TreuMoDa (Data Trust Model)*¹⁰ from the Karlsruhe Institute for Technologie (KIT)¹¹ and *the Semantic MediaWiki as a Research Tool* presented by Michael Freiberg (University of Gießen).

2.2 CROSS COLLABORATIONS AND CITIZEN SCIENCE

The conference was also an opportunity to share experience between different EU and national funded projects, such as COESO¹², a sister TRIPLE project, also in OPERAS fold. The COESO coordinator and communication officer were both present and attended the workshop #3 to connect within-discipline infrastructures in support of cross-disciplinary collaborations (9 participants). The new RDA Tiger project¹³, presented by the keynote speaker, Ari Asmi, raised particular interest in the challenge of multilingualism, one of the pillars of the GoTriple platform. To share experience and views on multilingualism, the TRIPLE project was invited to attend a workshop about multilingualism in Berlin at the end of March. RDA TIGER is an Horizon Europe project (HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01) intended to provide support services for the Working Groups (WGs) within the Research Data Alliance. OPERAS contribution to the project is a pilot dedicated to the set-up of an RDA WG about « Multilingual vocabularies alignment ». In line with TRIPLE's achievements, the pilot was presented to the community in the TRIPLE workshop organised by DARIAH on 27-28 March in Berlin on the « Use of Vocabularies for metadata curation and quality assessment in Social Sciences and Humanities ». This event was also the occasion to highlight the work carried out in TRIPLE for creating a multilingual SSH vocabulary and confront it with other similar experiences in the wider EOSC landscape.

The Translations and Open Science project¹⁴, led by OPERAS explores translation as one of the possible ways to disseminate research results in different languages. The project has a special focus on translation technology to optimise and mutualise translation processes, resources and tools. Susanna Fiorini, the scientific coordinator of this project presented the project and noticed a clear opportunity for the scientific translation to use the GoTriple platform and notably the terminology extraction from disciplinary vocabularies and research of references and constitution of corpus. Following the conference, a blog post¹⁵ was published to highlight the possible contribution of GoTriple to the scientific translation and share the improvements to be made to make this contribution tangible.

¹⁰ <https://www.treumoda.de/>

¹¹ <https://www.kit.edu/english/index.php>

¹² <https://coeso.hypotheses.org> : H2020 funded project on the Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020) SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325.

¹³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger>

¹⁴ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/translations-and-open-science>,

¹⁵ <https://tradso.hypotheses.org>

The final conference conveyed the concrete outcomes of the project to a broad audience, the reuse of technical building blocks of the platform, the OS training toolkit¹⁶ and also accelerated concrete synergies and collaboration opportunities beyond SSH such as a multidisciplinary approach for call for projects, which enlarged the users categories to translators for instance, and also served as a stepping stone to converge various initiatives in computer science and data mining. The presentations are deposited on Zenodo and are accessible in open access. All speakers gave their formal agreement to reuse and share their presentations licensed via a CC-BY license, while a takeaway brochure¹⁷ was printed and distributed. This brochure sums up the features of the platform, its objectives and impacts and gives direct access to the TRIPLE APIs, controlled vocabulary, training toolkit and the main scientific publications submitted during the project.

2.3 Tools

Additional to formal presentations, an informal poster session was set up at the end of the first day to invite researchers to present different tools and services.. Among the four sessions, two were coming from colleagues who are not part of the TRIPLE consortium¹⁸, one about managing humanities data, from a survey at the University of Bologna¹⁹ and one about Open Science from the United Nations Depository Libraries System. The two others highlighted innovation work from OPERAS research infrastructure and the DARIAH Lab about interdisciplinarity collaboration of Humanities and Technology²⁰.

¹⁶ DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6256197.

¹⁷ TRIPLE conference Key Takeaways : [10.5281/zenodo.7711891](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711891)

¹⁸1.Bianca Gualandi, Silvio Peroni, Luca Pareschi. Managing humanities data: some takeaways from a survey at the University of Bologna

2.Deborah Grbac. Open Science and digital humanities in the United Nations Depository Libraries System

3.Judith Schulte. OPERAS – Research Infrastructure for Open Scholarly Communication

4.Marta Błaszczczyńska, Malgorzata Guzik, Tomasz Hoffmann, Tomasz Umerle, Ireniusz Bloch. Dariah Lab: Interdisciplinary Collaboration of Humanities and Technology.

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7600316>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7622356>

3 | POTENTIAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR COLLABORATION

Three keynote speakers were invited to share their view on collaboration in the SSH with the audience research and offer long term perspectives to researchers and engineers to help them drive their work to bear challenges about SSH Research and Open Science :

- Leslie Chan, Director, Knowledge Equity Lab from the Department of Global Development Studies in the University of Toronto Scarborough shared his view about the production of knowledge in Artificial Intelligence.
- The professor Andrea Rapp from the "Technische Universität Darmstadt" gave a talk about the impact of Open Science on the research community and its visibility.
- Ari Asmi, Director of the Research Data Alliance AISBL (European RDA) Ari gave his personal view about the internationalisation of European Open Science initiatives and proposed new pathways from research to global interoperability developed in RDA²¹. This encounter resulted in a working group taking place end of March in Berlin between RDA Tiger initiative²² and TRIPLE project to work on multilingualism.

Presentation of the keynote speakers are openly accessible under the DOI:

- Andrea Rapp: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704572>
- Lesli Chan: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704640>
- Ari Asmi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705094>
- Conference in general, including brochure: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704571>

On several occasions, during the presentation and notably in the concluding word of Suzanne Dumouchel, the scientific coordinator of the project, the final conference was presented as the next step to ensure the sustainability of the platform and engage the SSH community in the use of the platform.

For this purpose, several representatives of the OPERAS AISBL attended the conference and took part in several presentations : They all took an active part in presenting or chairing a session which confirmed the seamless implication of OPERAS AISBL in the maintenance and sustainability of the platform.

Also all services providers attended the event, showing their commitment beyond the project period to maintain the services integrated in the platform :

- Gaël Wan Weyenbergh from MEOH for the Trust Building System,
- Luca de Santis and Tiziana Lombardo from Net7 for PUNDIT
- Gert Breiffuss and Leonie Disch from Know-Center for the Recommender System
- Peter Kraker from OKMAP for the Visualisation tool
- Suzanne Dumouchel and OPERAS members for the crowdfunding platform

OPERAS core members were also present and notably, Michael Kaiser, research manager at the MWS, Jadranka Stonajonvski associate professor in Zadar University and other representatives of Coimbra University and CNR.

²¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger> : Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions (RDA TIGER)

CONCLUSION

The final conference conveyed the concrete outcomes of the project to a broad audience, the reuse of technical building blocks of the platform, the OS training toolkit and also accelerated concrete synergies and collaboration opportunities beyond SSH such as a multidisciplinary approach for call for projects, which enlarged the users categories to translators for instance, and also served as a stepping stone to converge various initiatives in computer science and data mining.

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